

CAMPHOROSMA MONSPELIAVA L. (synonym Lessingii LITV. - A VALUABLE FODDER PLANT FOR RECLAMATION OF SALINE AND DROUGHT-PRONE AGRICULTURAL LANDSCAPES

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Abstract. This article presents recent findings on the status of natural populations of *Camphorosma* as a valuable wild fodder salt-loving species that grows in deserts and semi-deserts of Uzbekistan and around Issyk-kuli Lake in Kyrgyzstan. *Camphorosma* seeds and seedlings were planted on hypersaline soils in Karabuga (Karakalpakstan) in a mixed halophytic farming system. Cultivation technology, forage biomass accumulation and seed yield of *Camphorosma* on highly saline soils were documented. Practical recommendations for rangeland conservation and management using *Camphorosma* have been proposed.

Keywords: halophytes, salinity management, fodder species, yield, pasture conservation

Introduction: Due to the increasing prevalence of stresses such as drought, salinity and high temperatures, the interest in using wild halophytes as crop plants has increased. The most salinity-resistant halophyte species are gradually being introduced into production worldwide as a source of feed and raw materials for livestock, food, landscaping and pharmaceutical industries. In the last 15-20 years, large-scale comprehensive studies have been conducted to study the wild flora of halophytes in the Aral Sea Basin (1). The natural flora of the deserts and semideserts of Uzbekistan is rich in representatives of wild halophytes, mainly due to genera belonging to the family Amaranthaceae (former Chenopodiaceae). *Camphorosma monspeliaca* L is a C₄-non succulent euhalophyte, which tolerates cold winters and it is best suited to the sharply continental climate in Central Asian desert and semideserts. On the open pastures it is well grazed by domestic and wild animals due to its highly nutritional forage for small ruminants and camels. Well, consumed during fall and winter period after leaching of mineral substances. It is important to suggest that *Camphorosma* species is recommended for improvement and/or creation of long-term, mainly autumn-winter pastures. Expected yield of *Camphorosma* plant community in the Artemisia desert and semidesert rangelands varies 0.06 to 1.2 t DM/ha. During early stage of vegetation significant amount of mineral salt, volatile oil, microelements and amino acids are available in its aboveground biomass. *Camphorosma monspeliaca* L. is known to be a source of essential oils and alkaloids and has medicinal value as a stimulant, aphrodisiac, diuretic, and diaphoretic; it is also used to treat lung diseases (2). However, due to climate change, species of

the genus *Camphorosma* are close to being threatened and endangered, as they have been identified as needing attention for conservation and sustainable management.

The main goal of our article were studies of floristic composition, population size and seasonal dynamics of fodder biomass of *Camphorosma monspeliaca* L. under its natural habitat in different rangelands plant communities. The specific objective was technology for creation of artificial agrophytocenoses with participation of *Camphorosma* on salt affected abandoned lands in Karakalpakstan.

Research materials and methods: The description of vegetation taking into account its floristic composition was carried out using the Drude method generally accepted in geobotany [3]. The traditional route method of geobotanical studies, as well as methods of office interpretation of satellite images Landsat, MODIS, Google. Literature data were used to clarify the habitats of plant associations and their key species. To study the seasonal dynamics of forage biomass in control pasture plots, transects of 10 m² were laid out, cutting and analyzing the biomass yield. Plant samples at the end of vegetation were used for detecting of nutritional value under laboratory condition using standard methods [4]. Categories of pastures were identified in accordance with the scheme of pasture typology of Uzbekistan (Methodological recommendations for geobotanical survey of natural fodder basis of pastures of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 1980) [3]. The areas of the contours were determined using GIS methods. Phenology of plants was carried out according to the method of I. N. Beideman [5]. The species taxonomic nomenclature was identified using Central Asian plant guides and the Keys to the Central Asian Plants identifier (vol. I-X, 1968-1993), as well as according to the global taxonomic classification. Soil salinity was determined using a portable pH & EC tester - Hanna pH / Conductivity / and total dissolved salts (TDS).

An experimental site (ES) "Karabuga" for evaluation of growth characteristics of wild halophytes was established on the abandoned saline farmer lands in the irrigated massive "Karabuga", Karauzyak district in Karakalpakstan. Karauzyak district is one of the most vulnerable areas in the region due to lack of irrigation water, high soil salinity, severe effects of desertification and salt dust storms.

Soil preparation for sowing/planting of halophytes (*Camphorosma* inclusive) at Karabuga experimental site met the requirements of a whole range of agrotechnical measures including high-quality plowing followed by laser planning. Such preparation improves the water, air and nutrient regime for plants, creates conditions for better moisture holding, preservation and economical use of soil moisture, uniform seeding depth to ensures successful growth and development of plants. Prior seed sowing the soil was loosened with a chisel and irrigation furrows were made. The slope of the area to be irrigated was set at a level of at least 5%. Considering the physical and mechanical properties of the irrigated soils the slope was increased to 10% or more.

Results and discussion:

Assessment of vegetation and botanic diversity description. Vegetation formation in the Aral Sea region proceeds strictly along the paths of the formation of desert-type plant communities of Central Asia, with predominantly halophytic and psammophytic tree-shrub formations of vegetation [6]. As a result of reconnaissance field work and geobotanical surveys of halophytic vegetation of the salt desert of the Aral Sea basin, about 126 plant species were documented. The electronic database of halophytes with a focus on rare, endangered and economically significant species of the desert flora of the Aral Sea basin were initiated. Many of

those described by us desert halophytes species should be included in the Global Biodiversity Information System (GBIF).

Pasture territories of Karakalpakstan occupy vast areas, and they serve a source for further development of fodder basis of desert-pastures and animal husbandry production. Due to significant salinization of the soil, halophytes dominate in the vegetation cover of pasture lands. Majority among them are characterized by relatively low nutritional and forage biomass and grain yields, narrow seasonality of plant palatability (mainly autumn-winter season). Our findings revealed that soil salinization on research target areas in the Delta of Amudarya was accompanied by a decrease in the richness of botanical diversity, convergence of plant communities and simplification of the spatial structure of vegetation cover. The vegetation changes are undergoing towards the predominance of different life forms of halophytes species with high salt tolerance thresholds. This shift represents a serious shift in biodiversity and ecosystem functions and poses a severe threat even for halophytic plant communities. Most noticeable for these saline areas flora is the relative richness of the Amaranthaceae followed by Asteraceae, Poaceae, Fabaceae, Brassicaceae and less Boraginaceae, Plumbaginaceae, Polygonaceae and others. The main natural halophytic vegetation of the pastures consists of poorly palatable species, such as species of genus *Zygophyllum oxianum*, *Suaeda salsa*, *Caragana halodendron*, *Aeluropus litoralis*, *Tamarix hispida*, *Halostachys caspica*, *Karelina caspia*, *Halimochnemis*.

Among halophytic flora there are many of native species, such as *Caroxylon* species, *Camphorosma*, *Atriplex*, *Alhagi*, *Suaeda* and others, which are suitable for reclamation of arid and semi-arid salt/affected lands. Succulent halophytes have a capacity to remove salts or accumulate salts in their aboveground biomass, thus enabling agricultural production of conventional crops like alfalfa, wheat, rice, corn, vegetables and others.

Besides that, the vegetation cover of salt affected agricultural lands, especially along irrigated channels, near artificial lakes and water bodies is diverse with the dominance of species of Phragmites, which is very well eaten by cattle at the beginning of the growing season. The average yield of such pastures is 0.28-0.7t/ha of edible mass. The local population cut young shoots of reeds and uses them for animal feed. With intensive collection of reed shoots, the aftergrowth is restored very quickly, otherwise the old plants become coarse and turn into poorly edible animal feed.

We focused on the evaluation of 78 wild species in the project area. However, only a limited number of species have a feed value for further introduction into the system (closed cycle) of arid halophytic agriculture. The best results in terms of accumulation of green biomass and formation of high-quality seeds were shown by halophytic species such as *Bassia scoparia*, *Atriplex nitens*, *Climacoptera aralensis*, *C. lanata*, *Suaeda salsa*, *Suaeda altissima*, *Camphorosma monosperma*, *Caroxylon sclerantha*, *Caroxylon orientalis*, *Caroxylon dendroides*, *Amaranthus virescens*, *Salicornia persica*, *Agropyron fragile*, *Artemisia halophylla*, *Alhagi pseudalhagi*, which are recommended to be grown both in pure crops and in various combinations with non-traditional underutilized crops such as *Sorghum bicolor*, *Pennisetum glaucum*, *Setaria italica*, *Chenopodium quinoa*, *Charthamnus tinctorius*, *Helianthus tuberosus*, *Vigna radiata*, *Sesame indicum*, *Glycine max* and species of genus *Amaranthus* [7,8]. Encouraging results on creation of artificial agrobiocenoses at "Karabuga" site were obtained using species of *Camphorosma*.

Evaluation of natural populations of *Camphorosma* and results on their cultivation on salt affected soils

Among the halophytic species, *Camphorosma monspeliaca* L. (synonym *Camphorosma lessingi* - subspecies *C. lessingi*) occupies an important place as a fodder crop (the consumption of camphorosma hay by cattle reaches 80%). In natural habitats, this semi-shrub has 25-80 cm height, short woody branches that form a turf on the soil with bunches of leaves and with ascending whitish annual shoots. The taproot system penetrates to a depth of 2-8 m: the projective cover of plant communities with *Camphorosma* reaches 85-90%. On the natural pasture stands camphorosma begins to vegetate in April, blooms in July, August, the fruits ripen in late October - early November. The duration of the vegetation period is 235 days. The yield of dry forage biomass in the fruit ripening phase reaches 0.5-1.2 t / ha, seeds - 0.03 t / ha. 100 kg of hay contains 3.4 kg of digestible protein, 26.8 feed units. As a salt-tolerant, frost-resistant and grazing-resistant plant, it is widely used to improve natural and create cultural long-vegetating autumn-winter pastures, can be used to improve solonetz and saline pastures. At the beginning of the growing season, a large number of mineral salts, essential oils, microelements and amino acids accumulate in plants, which allows the use of this plant in medical practice.

Due to the sparse cover of camphorosma in the conditions of Amudarya delta and across Ustuyurt (in the Aral Sea region), in fall period of 2023 we studied the thickets (populations) of camphorosma at its natural habitat on the salt marshes of the Farish district of the Jizzakh region of Uzbekistan and surrounding Issyk-Kul Lake in Kyrgistan.

As is shown on Figure 1 the camphorosma plant associations are concentrated on a gently sloping, slightly hummocky slope - the base of a small elevation (10-12 m) near Lake Issyk-Kul.

Soil under camphorosma at Issyk-kuli was represented by dry desert solonchak exposed to sand and silt-lake deposits accumulation. The soil surface is covered with semi-decomposed remains of camphorosma vegetation in the form of a salty dust-sand mixture. Visually, medium-strong salinization is detected on the soil surface, which can be traced throughout the entire soil profile, gradually decreasing to a depth of around 1 m.

The second natural biotype of seed collection of seeds of *Camphorosma* was surrounding Issyk-Kul Lake. Soil and water samples analyzed at laboratory were characterized by a high value of pH (12.02) pH and electrical conductivity of water (EC, mS/cm) as 5.43 mS / cm, respectively. Issu-Kuli populations of *camphorosma* grows as a landscape plant and prevails over other species of the community in terms of mass 45.6 ± 0.78 and cover 89.6 ± 1.33 . The population size is relatively constant. The most constant indicators are the average statistical population size 33.0 ± 0.44 , as well as green biomass. Data on the variation coefficient C_v indicate a slight variability of indicators 3.32-5.33%, which indicates the evenness of individuals in the natural population. The average varying indicator was the number of shoots C_v equal to 15.1% (Table 1).

Table 1. Projective plant coverage and growth parameters of *Camphorosma monospeliaca* L. in the natural population of Issyk-Kul region

№	Indicator	$M \pm m$	G	C_v	t
1	Plant weight, g	$45,6 \pm 0,78$	1,83	4,01	60,0
2	Projective cover, %	$89,6 \pm 1,33$	2,98	3,32	67,4
3	Projective cover	$33,0 \pm 0,44$	1,76	5,33	75,0
4	Number of shoots	$10,4 \pm 0,70$	1,57	15,1	14,9

Note: M is the arithmetic mean, m is the error of the mean, G is the standard deviation, C_v is the variation coefficient, t is the indicator of the study accuracy.

Yield of green forage biomass of *camphorosma* under natural conditions, at the fruit maturation stage, reaches 1.2-1.51 t/ha. At the end of the growing season, in November, animals grazed up to 70-85% of the plants. In 2022 and 2023 within the framework of the SATREPS project a mixed artificial agrobiocenoses were established at Karabuga experimental site using seeds of *camphorosma* (*Camphorosma monospeliaca* subs. *lessingii*) and (*Artemisia halophyla*), collected surrounding Issyk-Kuli area. The coordinates of seed collection are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Coordinates of the collection site of seeds and seedlings of forage plants 23.11.2023

№	Plants names	N	E	Alt, m
1	<i>Camphorosma lessingii</i>	40°39'40,1	067°06'26,4	274
2	<i>Artemisia halophyla</i>	40°39'34,5	067°03'59,1	279

Halophytes growth characteristics under cultivation at Karabuga experimental plot.

The objective of scientific research at the initial stage on Karabuga experimental plot was to study various species of halophytes, including *camphorosma*, under saline conditions with the aim of widely introducing them into forage production practice. In 2022, *camphorosma* was planted in the experimental field with seedlings and sown with seeds at the rate of 6 kg per one hectare. Field seed germination varied between 35-42% and seedling survival rate makes 85% at high and hypersaline soil salinity. The chemical analysis of the soil samples taken over the Karabuga site revealed a high content of salts both at the root zone areas and at the depth profile up to one meter. Moreover, the salt content increases from spring to autumn. In 2023, halophyte crops were concentrated on a small plot; on the rest of the plot, due to severe soil salinization and poor seed germination, the crops were sparse, with weeds predominating. The optimal time for

sowing fodder halophytes is winter-early spring (December-April), when precipitation (rains/snow) and soil temperatures reach a suitable low level. A natural stratification of seeds occurred under snow in winter time. The optimal seeding depth for camphorosma is 1-2 cm. Seeding rate of *Camphorosma* 6.0 kg/ha is recommended to achieve the desired plant density.

It is important to note that plant survival was high - up to 94.4%. The plant height was 32.5 ± 1.54 cm in spring, 48.4 ± 0.37 cm in autumn, the variation coefficient C_v for this trait in spring indicates insignificant variability of the indicators 8.18, in autumn 1.32%. Under 2023 conditions, the hay yield of camphorosma was 0.53 ± 0.15 t/ha, the coefficient of variation C_v for this trait also indicates a slight variability of the indicators of 4.90%. The seed yield was 30 ± 0.03 kg/ha, the coefficient of variation C_v was 1.90% (Table 3).

Table 3. Yield productivity indicators of *Camphorosma monspeliaca* subspecies *lessingi* at the Karabuga State Agricultural University (2023)

Number of plants, thousand pcs/ha*)		Height, cm		Yield, t/ha	
15.V	29. IX	15.V	29.IX	Dry weight	Seeds
36/100	34/94,4	$32,5 \pm 1,54$	$48,4 \pm 0,37$	$0.53 \pm 0,15$	$0,03 \pm 0,003$

Note: *) The numerator is the number of plants, the denominator is the survival rate

Conclusion.

Ensuring uninterrupted access to quality feed is one of the key issues in the development of animal husbandry production in Karakalpakstan. The small size of rural household plots limits the supply of feed to livestock bred by farmers. As a rule, households purchase additional feed for winter-spring feeding of livestock in local markets and neighboring areas. Grazing of livestock along roadsides and irrigation canals is widespread.

Definitely, such land use methods damage soil fertility and the ecosystem as a whole. At the same time, alternative agricultural methods, in the context of climate change, on the one hand, should generate income for the rural population and be more profitable, and on the other hand, be environmentally friendly (and serve the restoration of natural ecosystems - for their sustainable use and conservation. Due to the expansion of areas under grain crops, there is a decrease in irrigated areas under forage crops, which has led to an acute shortage of feed, both in pasture and on agricultural lands.

Camphorosma along with other wild halophytic species cultivated in a mixed halophytic farming on saline farmland with limited irrigation produced a huge amount of green biomass and high seed yield. Low winter temperature and snow stimulates seed germination under field conditions. The ability of halophytes to self-regenerate allows them to be used for multiple cutting and hay making. Multiple cutting of the above-ground biomass makes it possible to obtain easily edible fodder. The quality of the seeds is not affected by toxic salts, which allows the gradual introduction of these species into mixed halophytic to improve livestock feeding systems.

Non-traditional fodder halophytes, such as *Camphorosma monspeliaca* can be successfully cultivated at buffer and economic zones of the Lower Amu Darya Biosphere Reserve (LABR) that can be used as concentrated supplement feeding for Bukhara Deer (*Cervus elaphus Bactrianus*), which is inscribed into the IUCN Red List. However, the heavy granulometric

composition of the clay-loamy soils is less suitable for the cultivation of wild halophytes. Scenarios for different land use conditions under different climate change and soil salinization impacts are crucially needed in further investigation to find optimal cultivation techniques for the promotion CHMF on saline farmer lands.

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